

Impacts of Blended Strategy on Performance and Retention in Social Studies among Secondary School Students in Ika South Local Government Area, Delta State

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Abstract

This research explored the Impacts of Blended Strategy on Performance and Retention in Social Studies among Secondary School Students in Ika South Local Government, Delta State. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. Pre-test, post-test, control group, quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised of all upper basic class two (JSSII) Social Studies students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. A sample size of 120 Social Studies students were purposively selected using an intact class. The Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT), a verified researcher-made test with 45 multiple-choice questions about the subject of "culture and social values in UBEL Schools 2 (JSS2), was employed for data collection. The reliability coefficient (r) of 0.70 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson formula 20. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, and the hypotheses tested at the 0.05 alpha level using analysis of covariance. The study revealed among others that there was significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method. The study recommended that to enhance student performance and retention in Social Studies, schools should equip classrooms with necessary technology and integrate blended learning into the curriculum. Additionally, regular training should be provided for teachers to effectively implement and promote blended learning across both urban and rural settings.

Keyword: Social Studies, Blended Learning, Students' Performance, Retention, location

Introduction

Blended learning, which integrates traditional classroom methods with digital tools, has become a transformative approach in modern education. It offers students the opportunity to access learning materials both in-person and online, combining the structure of face-to-face instruction with the flexibility of digital resources. This dual approach fosters independent learning and critical engagement, giving students more control over their educational experience. In the context of Social Studies, where critical thinking, analysis of social issues, and understanding societal dynamics are essential, blended learning can significantly enhance student performance and retention by providing diverse learning modalities that cater to different learning styles (Ukor, 2023).

Blended learning allows Social Studies teachers to present content in dynamic and interactive ways. For instance, digital tools like online simulations, multimedia resources, and collaborative platforms enable students to explore real-world societal issues, promoting deeper engagement with complex topics. As highlighted by AbdulRaheem, Muraina and Esther (2024), the use of technology in blended learning environments helps students better understand abstract social concepts by offering a more interactive, personalized learning experience. This approach not only reinforces traditional classroom learning but also provides opportunities for students to apply knowledge through practical, real-life simulations and activities. Despite the many benefits of blended learning, its effectiveness is not evenly distributed among all students. A significant factor influencing its success is geographical location, which can greatly affect students' access to the necessary technological resources. Wang, Omar, Zakaria and Zulkifli (2024) noted that urban students often have better access to stable internet connections, digital devices, and educational technology, allowing them to take full advantage of blended learning environments. In contrast, students in rural or remote areas may face challenges such as poor internet connectivity, limited access to digital devices, and insufficient technical support (Henríquez & Hilliger, 2024). As a result, students in rural locations may struggle to fully engage with the online components of blended learning, potentially widening the performance gap

between urban and rural students. Cunningham (2022) emphasized that rural students' performance in blended learning is often negatively impacted by these barriers, making it difficult for them to keep up with their urban peers. Alvarez (2020) in his study revealed that students perceived blended learning as difficult to execute in classroom environment due to the absence of institutional policies on the use of blended learning, lack of ICT training/knowledge (technophobia), poor confidence to engage in blended learning approach, and limited access to computer laboratories. Hence, these were perceived to be hindrances in the implementation of blended learning.

Studies have consistently shown that students in blended learning environments perform better academically than those in traditional classrooms. According to a study by Ukor (2023), students who participated in blended learning outperformed their peers in Social Studies assessments, particularly in tasks requiring critical thinking and problem-solving. The flexibility of blended learning allows students to review materials at their own pace and revisit complex topics, leading to improved comprehension and retention of information. Dania (2022) further supported this finding, noting that the integration of digital tools in Social Studies enhances student motivation and engagement, particularly in topics involving societal analysis and critical thinking.

The issue of retention, or the ability of students to persist and complete their studies, is another critical factor in evaluating the success of blended learning. Studies suggest that blended learning environments which tend to offer greater flexibility and a more engaging learning experience, could improve student retention rates. According to Shikha and Baliya (2023) students in blended learning programme are more likely to persist in their studies because they can tailor their learning experiences to fit their personal schedules and learning preferences. In Social Studies, this flexibility is particularly valuable, as it would allow students to explore complex societal issues in greater depth through independent research and digital collaboration.

However, location may also affect retention rates. Students in rural areas, who may already face socio-economic challenges, are often further disadvantaged by the lack of reliable internet access and digital resources. This digital divide could lead to frustration, disengagement, and ultimately, lower retention rates among rural students (Wang et.al, 2024). The moderating role of location in blended learning effectiveness underscores the importance of digital equity. Without access to reliable internet, necessary devices, and technical support, students in rural areas are more likely to underperform or drop out (Bishop et.al, 2022). To address this, teachers and policymakers must work to bridge the digital divide by investing in digital infrastructure, providing technological resources to underserved areas, and offering additional support to students who face these challenges. Ensuring equitable access to blended learning experiences requires bridging the digital divide between urban and rural locations (Chidi-Onwuta et.al, 2022).

In Social Studies education, where understanding societal issues and critical engagement are key, it is vital to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to succeed in blended learning environments. This requires not only improving access to digital resources but also developing strategies to support students in rural and remote areas who may face additional challenges. By addressing geographical disparities and ensuring equitable access to digital tools and resources, teachers can help all students succeed in blended learning environments, ultimately improving both performance and retention in Social Studies education.

Despite the proven benefits of blended learning in enhancing student engagement, performance, and retention, its effectiveness in Social Studies education remains uneven, especially when factoring in geographic disparities. While urban students often have reliable access to digital tools and resources, rural students frequently face obstacles such as inadequate internet connectivity, limited access to digital devices, and minimal technical support. These disparities contribute to a significant gap in academic performance and retention between urban and rural students, highlighting the "digital divide" that impacts equitable access to educational opportunities. In Ika South Local Government, Delta State, where Social Studies is fundamental in developing critical thinking and understanding of societal issues, the limitations faced by rural students undermine the potential of blended learning to foster these essential skills. The challenges faced by these students often lead to disengagement and hindered academic growth, ultimately widening the performance gap between them and their urban counterparts. Addressing this digital divide is essential to ensure that all students, regardless of location, can benefit equally from blended learning in Social Studies. This study aims to explore the impact of blended learning on student performance and retention, with a particular focus on how geographical location moderates its effectiveness, to better inform strategies that can bridge this digital gap in educational outcomes.

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using blended strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.
2. Determine the mean performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.
3. Determine the mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using blended strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.
4. Determine the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using blended strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?
2. What is the mean performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?
3. What is the mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?
4. What is the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance for this study.

1. There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State
2. There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State
3. There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State
4. There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental, non-equivalent pre-test, post-test control group design to assess the performance and retention of Social Studies students using blended learning. The research population comprised all upper basic education students in public schools in Ika South Local Government Area. A sample of 120 Social Studies students from three intact, non-equivalent classes across two upper basic education schools was purposively selected and assigned to two experimental groups and one control group. The Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT), a validated researcher-designed instrument with 45 multiple-choice questions covering the topic of culture and social values for JSS2 Social Studies, was used for data collection. The reliability of the SSPT was determined using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20, yielding a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.70. The experimental groups were taught using blended learning models: the Social Studies flex blended model and the Social Studies flipped model. The control group, on the other hand, received instruction via the conventional teaching method. The SSPT was administered as both a pre-test and post-test to all groups, with a retention test conducted three weeks after the post-test. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to address the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at a significance level of 0.05.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores of students' performance taught Social Studies using social studies flex and flipped strategies and conventional method.

Teaching Strategies	N	Pre-test		Pre-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS flex blended model	40	40.1000	9.95968	78.7500	11.03282	50.65
SS flipped model	40	40.4000	9.39853	75.5500	10.05233	49.15
Conventional Method	40	35.4300	7.26199	54.6500	9.01069	30.20

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows that the mean score for the flex model was 50.65, the mean score for the flipped model was 49.15, and the mean score for the conventional method was 30.20. The flipped and flex blended learning models of blended strategy seem to perform better than the conventional approach, in contrast. This merely indicates that students who were taught Social Studies using the flex and flipped models outperformed those who were taught using the conventional method.

Research Question 2

What is the mean performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of Social Studies students' performance taught social studies using Social Studies flex blended model, Social Studies flipped model and conventional method based on location.

Teaching Strategies	Location	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS Flex model	Urban	25	31.0769	8.92059	70.6923	6.96491	59.6154
	Rural	15	28.2857	7.49921	62.2857	6.86132	35.0000
SS Flipped model	Urban	15	39.6364	7.24255	77.0000	6.34035	50.3636
	Rural	25	31.3222	10.79352	68.3322	9.39230	38.0000
Conventional Method	Urban	25	38.0000	9.29383	59.0000	10.98571	46.0000
	Rural	15	26.5000	8.68022	55.2150	8.39049	28.6142

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows that urban students had a mean gain of 59.6154, rural students 35.000 score for instruction under the flex model, urban students had a mean of 50.3636, and rural students 38.0000 for the flipped model, but urban and rural students scored 46.0000 and 28.6142, respectively, for the conventional method. The results showed that both urban and rural students did better with flex and flipped models than with the traditional method. As a result, students in urban and rural locations taught Social Studies utilizing flex and flipped models performed better than urban and rural students taught using the conventional method.

Research Question 3:

What is the mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of Social Studies students' retention scores taught Social Studies using Social Studies flex model, Social Studies flipped model and conventional method.

Teaching Strategies	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS flex blended model	40	78.8000	8.35542	78.2000	8.03282	1.53
SS flipped model	40	78.9000	6.98645	77.3500	6.32966	0.87
Conventional Method	40	61.5000	5.69521	62.0000	5.27021	0.60

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The table 3 above shows that students taught Social Studies using flex model have mean score of 1.53, flipped model 0.87 and conventional method 0.60 respectively. This implies that students taught Social Studies using the two (2) blended learning models had higher retention compared to the conventional method. Comparatively, flex and flipped models of teaching appears to have great effect on students' retention in Social Studies.

Research Questions 4

What is the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation scores of urban and rural Social Studies students' retention scores taught Social Studies using Social Studies flex blended strategy, Social Studies flipped strategy and conventional method.

Teaching Strategies	Location	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS Flex model	Rural	20	75.3750	6.52758	73.6250	6.75525	1.3300
	Urban	20	75.9167	7.93698	74.5833	5.96048	1.6764
SS Flipped model	Rural	20	72.6000	8.31597	72.0000	8.21511	0.5000
	Urban	20	73.2000	9.81967	74.7000	9.17543	0.5900
Conventional Method	Urban	20	62.4132	8.79125	60.8333	9.53212	0.4766
	Rural	20	61.2300	9.16418	61.3750	9.64761	0.3630

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The table 4 reveals that rural students taught with flex model had a mean retention score of 1.3300, urban students taught with flex model scored 1.6764 while rural students taught with flipped model obtained a score of 0.5000 and urban students taught with flipped model scored 0.5900 but the mean retention scores for both urban and rural students under the conventional method are 0.4766 and 0.3630 respectively. The result indicated that urban and rural students taught using flex and flipped models had higher retention in Social Studies compared to their counterparts taught with the conventional method.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Table 5: Result of Analysis of Covariance of Social Studies students' performance scores taught Social Studies with social studies flex blended model, Social studies flipped model and conventional method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3678.441a	3	882.812	11.802	.000
Intercept	22463.465	1	23463.465	371.782	.000
Pretest	88.708	1	89.708	1.074	.405
Methods	2677.188	2	1438.594	17.195	.000
Error	5628.542	60	85.653		
Total	271181.000	56			
Corrected Total	8306.983	61			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Table 5 shows that the flex model, flipped model, and conventional method have a significant difference in students' performance. The exact probability of 0.000 connected with the effect as a result of the teaching methods is less than 0.05, indicating significance. As a result, the hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there was a significant difference in teaching approach on the performance of Social Studies students. The results revealed a substantial difference in teaching strategies (flex model, flipped model, and conventional approach) on students' academic achievement in Social Studies.

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Hypothesis 2:

Table 6: Result of Analysis of Covariance of Social Studies students' performance scores taught Social Studies with Social Studies flex blended strategy, Social Studies flipped strategy and conventional method based on location.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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Corrected Model	1453.967a	2	686.986	6.983	.003
Intercept	30558.871	1	30558.871	197.860	.000
Pre-test	.316	1	.316	.002	.986
Location	1452.816	1	1372.725	12.957	.001
Error	5953.017	57	109.435		
Total	281161.000	60			
Corrected Total	7606.992	59			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The table 6 shows significant difference between teaching methods and location on students' performance in Social Studies. Results on the table show that the calculated F- value of 12.957 was significant at 0.001 which is less than 0.05 and therefore is significant at 0.05 level of probability. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning there was significant difference between teaching methods and location on students' performance in Social Studies. Similarly, the result revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Table 7: Result of Analysis of Covariance of methods on students' retention score in Social Studies.

Dependent Variable: Retention score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3201.189a	3	1043.625	19.199	.000
Intercept	15193.841	1	15193.841	257.181	.000
Pre-test	879.552	1	879.552	15.460	.000
Methods	2117.300	2	1068.200	20.420	.000
Error	3016.997	56	63.672		
Total	294961.000	60			
Corrected Total	6218.183	59			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The table 7 shows the significant difference between teaching methods on students' retention in Social Studies. Results on the table revealed that the calculated F-value of 20.420 was significant at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and therefore is significant at 0.05 level of probability. Consequently, the hypothesis is rejected hence, there was difference between teaching methods on students' retention in Social Studies. Therefore, the result indicated that there is a significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Table 8: ANCOVA analysis of urban and rural Social Studies students who were taught Social Studies with Social Studies flex blended model, Social Studies flipped model and conventional method based on retention.

Dependent Variable: Retention score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1089.802a	2	559.952	6.297	.005
Intercept	1870.167	1	10870.165	117.543	.000
Pretest 1	999.487	1	579.487	115.127	.003
Location	119.916	1	114.917	1.105	.004
Error	4318.278	58	67.060		
Total	18498.000	59			
Corrected Total	4417.174	62			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

In the table 8, it was indicated that location is significant among the groups (flex blended model, flipped model and conventional method). The result showed that the F-value of 1.105 obtained a significance of .004 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected hence, there is a significant difference between the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies with flex model, flipped model and conventional methods in Social Studies.

Discussion of Findings

Results in table 1 and 5 revealed that there is difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using the flex model, flipped model and conventional method. Comparatively, flex and flipped models appears to have a great effect on students' performance in Social Studies. This implies that students taught with flex and flipped models performed better than those taught using conventional method. This finding aligns with that of Ukor (2023) who asserted that students are more motivated to learn and performed better than those taught with conventional method. In the same vein, the finding of Barış Çiftçi (2020) revealed that a greater percentage of students taught using blended instructional strategy got excellent performance than the conventional classroom teaching style.

The results in table 2 and 6 indicated that there was significant difference in the performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method. The results showed that flex and flipped models for urban and rural students performed better than the conventional method. Wang et al (2024) opined that students taught in a blended learning environment in urban and rural communities performed far better than their counterparts taught using conventional approach. This finding was supported by Ashraf, Tsegay and Meijia (2021) who averred that blended strategy enables the teacher manage the blended learning classroom setting with confidence by addressing the intersection of pedagogy, technology, and subject knowledge.

The result in table 3 and 7 revealed that students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped models had greater retention compared to those taught under the conventional method. Therefore, since ($p < 0.05$), there is a significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method. This finding agrees with the views of Ukor (2023) who stated that retention level was higher for blended learning strategy compared to the conventional classroom teaching. Consequently, the result shows that the experimental subjects significantly improved in their post-test scores after treatment.

The result in table 4 and 8 indicated that urban and rural students taught using flex and flipped models had higher retention in Social Studies compared to their counterparts taught with the conventional method. In same vein, the hypothesis showed that location is significant among the groups (flex blended model, flipped model and conventional method). This finding agrees with that of Boateng. (2024) who asserted that through blended approach students retained subject content better compared to the traditional method. AbdulRaheem, Muraina and Esther-Uche (2024) contended that students learn and gain high comprehension in a blended learning environment more than in a traditional setting due to the fact that it offers the chance to develop engaging and dynamic learning opportunities.

Conclusion

The successful implementation of blended learning strategies such as the flex and flipped models would improve students' performance and retention in social studies. Blended learning enables students to explore, integrate knowledge, and facilitate collaborative learning, resulting in superior learning results. In comparison to the traditional method, the blended learning strategy has proven to be beneficial in teaching and learning, as well as boosting students' performance and retention in Social Studies in both urban and rural settings.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the study:

1. Social Studies teachers should actively promote and implement blended learning to enhance students' academic performance and retention in upper basic education.
2. Schools should be equipped with essential technology, including computer systems and internet access, to facilitate effective blended learning.
3. Both urban and rural students should be encouraged to engage with blended learning methods in social studies to bridge educational gaps and improve access.
4. Blended learning should be formally integrated into the social studies curriculum to standardize its use and benefits.

5. Schools and educational bodies should organize regular in-service training, workshops, and seminars for teachers to enhance their skills and knowledge in using blended learning effectively.

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References

- AbdulRaheem Yusuf, Muraina Olugbenga Omiyefa & Esther Uche Obiajulu-Anyia (2024) The Hybrid Classroom: Adapting Social Studies Education To The Blended Learning Landscape In Nigeria. *Journal of African social studies (JASS)*, 5, 1
- Alvarez Jr, A. V. (2020). Learning from the Problems and Challenges in Blended Learning: Basis for Faculty Development and Program Enhancement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 112-132.
- Ashraf, M. A., Tsegay, S. M., & Meijia, Y. (2021). Blended learning for diverse classrooms: Qualitative experimental study with in-service teachers. *Sage Open*, 11(3), 21582440211030623.
- Barış Çiftçi (2020) The Effect of Blended Learning on Academic Achievement and Attitudes at Social Studies Courses. *Open Journal for Educational Research* 4(2), 143-150.
- Bishop, S., Quintanilla-Muñoz, C., & Marshall III, T. (2022). Literature Review--Digital Equity and Inclusion for Education. *Equity Assistance Center Region II, Intercultural Development Research Association*.
- Boateng, S. K. B. (2024). *Rural school teachers' attitudes toward the use of technology in classroom assessments* (Doctoral dissertation, Montana State University-Bozeman, College of Education, Health & Human Development).
- Cunningham, J. (2022). *The Role of Self-Efficacy in Supporting Rural Teachers in the Implementation of Blended Learning*. Southern Nazarene University.
- Chidi-Onwuta, G., Iwe, N. N., & Chikamadu, C. P. (2022). Teaching English in Low Resource- Environments: Problems and Prospects. *Special Education*, 1(43).
- Devathosh, U. N. (2018). *The Impact of a Blended Curriculum and Selected Demographic Factors on Early College Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry* (Doctoral dissertation, Texas Southern University).
- Henríquez, V., & Hilliger, I. (2024). Blended learning in rural K-12 education: Stakeholder dynamics and recommendations. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*.
- Peter Ogbianigene Dania (2023) The new world: what should the pedagogy of Social studies advocate? (Being a Lead Paper at the 2022 SOSAN National Conference) *Nigerian journal of social studies*, vol. 26 (2)
- Shikha, D., & Baliya, J. N. (2023). Impact of Blended Learning Strategies on Concept Attainment among Elementary School Students Studying Social Studies-An Experimental Study. *Indian Journal of Natural Sciences*, 13, 76.
- Ukor, D. O. (2023). An investigation into social studies students' performance and retention using blended learning in upper basic education level schools in Delta State. *Journal of guidance and counselling studies*, 7(1), 141-156.
- Wang, I., Omar, M. K., Zakaria, N. S., & Zulkifli, N. N. (2024). Differential reactions of urban and rural teachers to blended learning: evidence from chinese secondary schools. *International journal of mobile and blended learning (IJMBL)*, 16(1), 1-19.